

**PATHOGENESIS AND PREVENTION OF NECROSIS IN THE CARDIOVASCULAR
SYSTEM**

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Introduction: A standard electrocardiogram is a 12-lead representation of the electrical activity of the heart, representing the difference in electrical potential between positive and negative electrodes placed on the limbs and chest. Six of these leads are vertical (taken from leads I, II, and III located on the front and electrodes located on the limbs - aVR, aVL, aVF) and 6 are horizontal (located in the precordial region - V1, V2, V3, V4, V5, and V6). The 12-lead ECG can be an important imaging test for establishing a number of cardiac diagnoses (see the ECG changes interpretation chart), including

Conditions predisposing to syncope or sudden death (e.g., Brugada syndrome, long QT syndrome, Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome)

Standard components of an electrocardiographic complex

It is generally accepted to divide the ECG curve into the P wave, PR interval, QRS complex, QT interval, ST segment, T wave, and U wave (see ECG waveform diagram).

P wave = reflects atrial depolarization. PR interval = time interval from the onset of atrial depolarization to the onset of ventricular depolarization. QRS complex = ventricular depolarization, consisting of Q, R, and S waves. QT interval = time between the onset of ventricular depolarization and ventricular repolarization. RR interval = time interval between two complexes. T wave = ventricular repolarization. ST segment + T wave (ST-T) = ventricular repolarization. U wave = probably after ventricular depolarization (relaxation).

Research methods and materials:

Typically, the QRS interval is 0.07-0.10 seconds. A complex duration of 0.10-0.11 seconds, depending on the changes in the shape of the QRS complex, is considered to be an incomplete bundle branch block or a nonspecific intraventricular conduction delay. An interval duration of ≥ 0.12 seconds indicates a complete bundle branch block or a delay in intraventricular conduction.

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Normally, the QRS axis is from 90 to -30° . A value of the cardiac electrical axis from -30° to -90° is considered a deviation of the cardiac electrical axis to the left and is observed in the left anterior bundle branch block of the bundle of His (-60°) and inferior myocardial infarction.

A value of the electrical axis of the heart from 90° to 180° is considered a deviation of the electrical axis of the heart to the right; It is observed in any condition that leads to increased pulmonary pressure and hypertrophy of the right ventricle of the heart (cor pulmonale, acute pulmonary embolism, pulmonary hypertension) and sometimes occurs with a block of the right or posterior branch of the left bundle of His.

QT interval

The time interval between the beginning of ventricular depolarization and the end of their repolarization. The QT interval should be calculated taking into account the heart rate using the following formula:

Research results:

Where QT_c is the expected value of the QT interval and RR is the time interval between two QRS complexes. All intervals are recorded in seconds. The normal range of QT_c in adults is 350-450 ms in men and 360-460 ms in women. Prolongation of the QT_c interval is closely associated with the development of torsades de pointes. Determining the QT_c interval is often difficult because the end of the T wave is often poorly defined or there are many drugs that prolong the QT interval (see CredibleMeds).

ST segment

The ST segment reflects the end of ventricular myocardial depolarization. Normally, it is located horizontally on the isoline similar to the PR (or TP) interval or slightly shifted from the isoline.

T wave

Reflects ventricular repolarization. It usually has the same direction as the QRS complex (opposite direction (discordant) may indicate current or past MI); the T wave is usually flattened, rounded, but may be low-amplitude in hypokalemia and hypomagnesemia, and sharp-edged in hyperkalemia and hypocalcemia.

U wave

The U wave usually occurs in patients with hypokalemia, hypomagnesemia, or ischemia. The U wave is often present in healthy individuals.

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The electrodes for right chest leads are placed on the right side of the chest wall in a mirror image of the standard left chest electrodes. They are labeled V1R–V6R; sometimes only V4R is used as the most sensitive lead for diagnosing right ventricular myocardial infarction.

For additional unipolar leads, electrodes can be placed in the 5th intercostal space, V7 near the posterior axillary line, V8 near the midscapular line, and V9 at the left edge of the spine. These leads are rarely used, but they can be especially useful in diagnosing true posterior myocardial infarction.

Esophageal torsion

The esophageal lead is located significantly closer to the atrium than the external leads. It is used when the P wave is not recorded on a standard ECG, as well as when it is necessary to determine the electrical activity of the atria during tachycardia with a wide ventricular complex (the need to check its atrial or ventricular variant) or if atrioventricular dissociation is suspected. The esophageal lead can also be used for intraoperative monitoring of myocardial ischemia or for determining atrial activity during cardioplegia. The patient swallows the lead, which is then attached to a conventional electrocardiograph, most often to lead II port.

Continuous ST segment monitoring

Continuous ST segment monitoring is used to detect ischemia and severe arrhythmias. Monitoring can be automated (special electronic monitors are available) or performed during clinical analysis of a series of electrocardiograms. Indications include intensive care unit monitoring in patients with worsening angina, post-operative monitoring, intraoperative monitoring, and postoperative follow-up.

QT interval dispersion

The QT interval variance (the difference between the longest and shortest intervals on a 12-lead ECG) has been proposed as a method for assessing myocardial repolarization heterogeneity. Increased variance (≥ 100 milliseconds) indicates electrical heterogeneity of the myocardium due to ischemia or fibrosis, which increases the risk of reentrant arrhythmias and sudden death. Variance may be a predictor of mortality risk, but is rarely measured because measurement error is widespread and values often overlap between patients with heart disease and healthy individuals, there are no limits to the possible error, and other risk criteria exist for these conditions.

Results: The use of event sensors allows for continuous monitoring of the patient for up to 30 days, during which time it is possible to detect rare rhythm disturbances that are missed during 24-hour Holter monitoring. The recorder can be activated by the patient during continuous

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operation or at the onset of symptoms. The device's memory allows you to store information about events that occurred a few seconds before and after activation. The patient can send ECG data to a doctor for interpretation by telephone or via satellite; Some recorders can automatically transmit information about serious events. If the patient has significant events (for example, fainting) that occur more often than once every 30 days, an event recorder can be implanted under the skin (implantable loop recorder). It is activated by a small magnet. The battery life of the subcutaneous recorder is several years.

Summary: Some consumer-grade smartwatches take ECGs from the wrist. Smartwatches are capable of detecting arrhythmias in real time and are being explored for use in this area.

Traditional CT and MRI scans are limited in their use because the heart is constantly beating, but if the rhythm is regular and the heartbeat is monitored, faster CT and MRI techniques provide diagnostic images of the heart. Sometimes patients are given medications (such as beta blockers) to slow the heart rate during the test.

With ECG synchronization, the recorded (or reconstructed) image is synchronized with the electrocardiogram (ECG), which allows data from different phases of the cardiac cycle to be combined to create single images of the individual stages of heart contraction.

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